

Internet of Things Centric-Based Spam Prediction in Smart Home Environment Application: A Review

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Abstract— The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has revolutionized the concept of smart homes, offering unprecedented convenience and connectivity. However, this interconnectedness also brings forth new challenges, notably in safeguarding against cyber threats such as spam. With the increasing complexity and diversity of IoT ecosystems within smart homes, conventional spam detection methods are often inadequate. Hence, there arises a pressing need for innovative approaches tailored to the unique characteristics of IoT environments. This review aims to explore the current landscape of IoT-centric spam prediction techniques specifically designed for smart home applications. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, this review synthesizes the various methodologies, challenges, and future directions in this burgeoning field.

Keywords— Smart home, Spam, Machine, IOT, Detection, Security, AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of IoT technology has catalyzed a paradigm shift in the way we interact with our living spaces, giving rise to the concept of smart homes. These modern abodes are equipped with an array of interconnected devices ranging from smart thermostats and lighting systems to security cameras and voice assistants, all seamlessly integrated to enhance convenience, comfort, and efficiency. However, this unprecedented level of connectivity also presents a double-edged sword, exposing smart homes to a myriad of cybersecurity threats, with spam being a prominent concern.

Spam, in the context of smart homes, refers to unsolicited or unwanted messages, often disseminated through various communication channels such as emails, text messages, or voice calls, targeting both users and IoT devices within the home network. Unlike traditional spam encountered in email inboxes, IoT-centric spam in smart homes can manifest in diverse forms, including malicious firmware updates, deceptive voice commands, or fraudulent sensor data injections. Moreover, the distributed and heterogeneous nature of IoT ecosystems complicates spam detection, as conventional methods designed for centralized networks are ill-suited to handle the intricacies of smart home environments.

To address these challenges, researchers and practitioners have increasingly turned their attention towards developing specialized spam prediction techniques tailored to the unique characteristics of IoT-centric smart homes.

These approaches leverage the interconnectedness of IoT devices, the richness of sensor data, and advanced machine learning algorithms to proactively identify and mitigate spam-related threats. By analyzing patterns of device interactions, anomalous behavior, and contextual cues, these systems aim to distinguish legitimate activities from potentially malicious ones, thereby enhancing the security and privacy of smart home occupants.

In recent years, a growing body of literature has emerged focusing on IoT-centric spam prediction in smart home environments. This literature encompasses a diverse array of methodologies, including anomaly detection, behavior analysis, machine learning, and blockchain-based solutions, each with its strengths and limitations. However, despite the progress made, several challenges persist, such as the scalability of detection algorithms, the integration of heterogeneous IoT devices, the management of false positives, and the preservation of user privacy.

This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the state-of-the-art in IoT-centric spam prediction within smart home environments. By synthesizing existing research findings, identifying key trends, and elucidating persistent challenges, this review seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding cybersecurity in IoT ecosystems. Moreover, by highlighting potential avenues for future research and innovation, this review endeavors to inspire the development of more effective and resilient spam prediction systems capable of safeguarding the integrity and security of smart homes in an increasingly connected world.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

T. Perumal et al.,[1] present system collects the real-time data collected using IMU sensors and transmitted to the IoT-Edge Server via Wi-Fi where the data has been fused and classified using light-weight deep learning models. This system has a provision of a Web-based dashboard which is helpful for the home dwellers to monitor the activities in the remote. The performance evaluation justified that the developed system can measure IoT-based activity recognition with greater efficiency in terms of accuracy and F1-score in a shorter response time as of deployment in the cloud platform to detect the activity.

A. Makkar et al.,[2] presented the security of the IoT devices by detecting spam using ML. To achieve this objective, Spam Detection in IoT using Machine Learning framework is proposed. In this framework, five ML models are evaluated using various metrics with a large collection of inputs features sets. Each model computes a spam score by considering the refined input features. This score depicts the trustworthiness of IoT device under various parameters. REFIT Smart Home data set is used for the validation of proposed technique. The results obtained prove the effectiveness of the proposed scheme in comparison to the other existing schemes.

A. Makkar et al.,[3] presents the dataset WEBSpam-UK 2007 with respect to accuracy and overhead generated. From the results obtained, it has been demonstrated that CSF improves the accuracy by 97.3%, which is comparatively high in comparison to the other existing approaches in literature.

G. Fortino et al.,[4] propose a framework for agents operating in an IoT environment, called ResIoT, where the formation of communities for collaborative purposes is performed on the basis of agent reputation. In order to validate our approach, we performed an experimental campaign by means of a simulated framework, which allowed us to verify that, by our approach, devices have not any economic convenience to perform misleading behaviors. Moreover, further experimental results have shown that our approach is able to detect the nature of the active agents in the systems (i.e., honest and malicious) , with an accuracy of not less than 11 % compared to the best competitor tested and highlighting a high resilience with respect to some malicious activities.

K. A. Al-Thelaya et al.,[5] suggest two representation models for social interaction's graph-based datasets. The representation models are mainly developed based on analyzing interactions and relations between users. The first model is developed based on graph-based analysis, while the other one is developed based on sequential processing of user interactions. Based on the conducted experiments, we

conclude that the two representation models show high spam detection accuracy. However, graph-based analysis models produce higher accuracy levels compared to those produced by interaction sequences processing models.

T. Y. Ho et al.,[6] focus on the traffic behavior that we only consider the features of source IP, destination IP, timestamp of connection, and quantity of connection. To conquer the black box of complicated network traffic, this work applies the deep learning paradigm and proposes the variant version of VGG16 to examine the features within traffic flow. Finally, this paper proposes a method to support more explanation on traffic behavior with learning model.

J. Zhang et al.,[7] proposes a method based on Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network(WGAN) to generate malicious PDF files which are similar to benign ones and can evade the malicious file detection system. The experimental results show that the adversarial examples generated by our method can evade the PDF classifier-PDFrate of 100%. We also test their performance in different classifiers and the results show that our proposed method can evade the classifiers of different machine learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machine(SVM), Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forest.

A. Makkar et al.,[8] presents webpage filtering algorithm is proposed which automatically detects the spam web pages. The spam webpages are detected before these are processed by the ranking module of search engines. The machine learning model, i.e., decision tree is used for the validation of the proposed scheme. The tenfold cross validation approach is used to improve the accuracy of model, i.e., 98.2%. The results obtained demonstrate that the proposed scheme has the power of preventing the spam web pages in Cognitive Internet of Things (CIoT) environment.

A. K. Singh et al.,[9] apply each classifier without selecting any features in order to experiment on the dataset and examine the outcome. Next, to select the desired features we apply best first feature selection algorithm and apply various algorithms for classification. We found that the accuracy has improved when we applied feature selection process in the experimentation.

T. Lange et al.,[10] present a review on botnet evolution, trends and mitigations, and offer related examples and research to provide the reader with quick access to a broad understanding of the issues at hand.

T. Qiu et al.,[11] provides intelligent identification of spammers without relying on flexible and unreliable relationships. SIGMM combines the presentation of data, where each user node is classified into one class in the construction process of the model. We validate the SIGMM

by comparing it with the reality mining algorithm and hybrid fuzzy c-means (FCM) clustering algorithm using a mobile network dataset from a cloud server. Simulation results show that SIGMM outperforms these previous schemes in terms of recall, precision, and time complexity.

G. Kumar et al.,[12] Social Networking plays a very important part in our day to day life to share our views on various issues those arise. As it opened new means of communication between masses to share their thoughts. The data from these sites can be very useful for the purpose of analysis.

III. CHALLENGES

There are some challenges to these techniques. Some of them are highlighted below:

- In trust modeling system user's trust tends to vary over time according to the user's experience and involvement of social networks.

Only a few approaches deals with the dynamics of trust by distinguishing between recent and old tags. Future work considering dynamics of trust would lead to better modeling in real world application.

- Most of the existing approaches based on text information assuming monolingual environment.

- However social network services are used by people from various countries, so various languages simultaneously appears in tags and comment. In such cases some text information may be regarded as wrong or considered as spam due to language spam. Therefore incorporating multilinguism in trust modeling would solve this problem.

It is observed that interaction across social network become popular. For e.g. users can use their Facebook accounts to log in some other social network services. Thus future challenge is to investigate how trust model across domains can be effectively connected and shared.

- Trust modeling most of the current techniques for noise and spam reduction focus only on textual tag processing and user profile analysis while audio and visual content features of multimedia content can also provide useful information about the relevance of the content and content tag relation. In future challenge could be to combine multimedia content analysis with the conventional tag processing and user profile analysis.

IV. CONCLUSION

The review of Internet of Things (IoT) centric-based spam prediction in smart home environments underscores the critical importance of addressing cybersecurity challenges in the era of interconnected devices. As smart homes become increasingly ubiquitous, the threat landscape

continues to evolve, necessitating innovative approaches to mitigate spam-related threats effectively. Despite the progress made in developing IoT-centric spam prediction techniques, numerous challenges persist, ranging from the heterogeneity of IoT devices to scalability, privacy preservation, and adaptability. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort from researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to develop holistic solutions that safeguard the integrity, security, and privacy of smart home occupants. The attackers can flood the target database with unwanted requests to stop IoT devices from having access to various services. These malicious requests produced by a network of IoT devices are commonly known as bots. DDoS can exhaust all the resources provided by the service provider. It can block authentic users and can make the network resource unavailable. These are the attacks imposed at the physical layer of IoT device.

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